

IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS FOR TUTORIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract:

The article under discussion is devoted to the description of the ways of improving the pedagogical system of preparation of future teachers for tutorial activity. The author of the article considers that the technology of tutorial activity should consist of the following components: methods, techniques, modes of work, sequence of operations and procedures. Technologies promote formation of ethical and valuable attitude in students to the world, to people and to themselves.

Key words: tutoring activity, pedagogical technology, planning, providing, assessing, managing, educational, social-educational, problems.

Introduction

Despite the fact that tutorial activity is a specific type of pedagogical activity, carried out with the help of specific technologies, we have made an attempt to define "technologies of tutorial activity" on the basis of the concept of "pedagogical technology". The most broad definition of pedagogical technology, published by the Association for Pedagogical Communication and Technology in the United States, was taken as the basis: "Pedagogical technology is a complex, integrative process that includes people, ideas, tools and ways of organizing activities for problem analysis and planning, providing, assessing and managing problems related to all aspects of knowledge acquisition"[5].

Based on the volume of this definition, it remains only to clarify the specialization of tutorial activity, that is, under the technology of tutorial activity we will understand a complex, integrative process that includes people, ideas, means and ways of organizing tutorial activity for its analysis, planning, implementation and control.

The main part

The technological approach to teaching and communication occupies an important place in the technology of tutorial activity, which implies instrumental support of tutorial activity with a guarantee of achieving the set goal. The

pedagogical and social reality [3; 4] is realized in tutoring, which allows to a large extent:

- 1) to predict the results of tutor activity and manage the processes of its realization;
- 2) to analyze, systematize and use effectively the practical experience of tutor activity;
- 3) solve educational and social-educational problems in complex;
- 4) provide favorable conditions for personal development;
- 5) to choose the most effective and develop new methods and ways of solving social and pedagogical problems, inevitably arising in the process of active tutorial activity.

The technology of tutorial activity regarding the theoretical and practical approach to education occupies mainly the process-activity level being characterized as a process of interaction between subjects and objects in tutorial activity, their goal setting, planning, organization, goal realization and results analysis.

As far as organizational structures are concerned, tutoring is a macrotechnology, i.e. branch educational technology which defines a tutor-teacher's activity as aimed at teaching, education or support in the context of an academic discipline or an individual educational trajectory.

Based on the definition of the key term "technology", more precisely, on its original meaning (*techne* - "skill, art"; *logos* - "science"), we agree with the opinion that the goal of technology is to break down the process of achieving a certain result into its component parts [1]. On this basis, the technology of tutorial activity, in our opinion, should consist of the following components: methods, techniques, modes of work, sequence of operations and procedures, direct dependence on directly used means, equipment, tools and materials.

Technology of tutor activity assumes thought-out and well-organized psychological and pedagogical support, which consists in helping students to identify and reveal their abilities, to correlate their desires with real existing opportunities, to determine the prospects for growth and progress in personal development, in orientation in a rapidly changing world. During the whole period of training a student needs guidance and support, which includes effective response to arising issues, ensuring the implementation of needs as they arise.

When analyzing the tutoring system as a means of improving the quality of education we cannot but agree with the conclusions of many scientists, based on

statistical data from leading universities in the world, that the improvement of academic achievements of higher education students and school students is directly related to the tutoring system. According to Cavelti, in this system there is the learning process which is adapted to the needs of students [1].

One of the technologies actively used in mastering tutoring is the *case-study method*.

The method of case-study or the method of concrete situations. Case method is a method of active problem-situation analysis based on learning by solving concrete tasks - situations (case solving). This method belongs to the non-game imitative active teaching methods.

The immediate goal of the case-study method: the joint efforts of a group of students to analyze a "case" situation arising from a particular situation and to develop a practical solution; the end of the process is to evaluate the proposed algorithms and choose the best one in the context of the problem posed.

The case-study method has been most widely used, first of all, in teaching economics and business sciences abroad (it was first used in the educational process at Harvard University Law School in 1870). However, it should be noted that the case method is currently one of the leading active methods of teaching, which provides an outlook on social, pedagogical and other realities.

As a technology of collective learning case integrates other technologies. First of all, these are technologies of developmental, person-centered learning, which include procedures of individual, group and collective development. They promote formation of ethical and valuable attitude in students to the world, to people and to themselves.

If we talk about the general characteristics of the method, the following features are worth highlighting.

The method is designed for knowledge acquisition in disciplines whose science is pluralistic, the task of teaching is oriented to obtaining not one, but many truths and orientation in their problem field; the emphasis of learning is transferred not on mastering ready-made knowledge, but on its development, on the co-creativity of the student and the teacher; the result of method application is not only knowledge, but also skills of professional activity; the technology of the method: according to certain rules, a model of a concrete situation that has occurred in real life is developed and the set of knowledge and practical skills that students need to acquire is reflected.

The advantage of this method: not only getting knowledge and formation of practical skills, but also development of students' system of values,

professional positions, life attitudes, peculiar professional world-view and world-transformation.

The classical defect of traditional teaching connected with "dryness" and unemotional presentation of material is overcome. As an intellectual product, the case has its own sources. In particular, the source material can be:

- social life in all its diversity is the source of the story, the problem and the factual basis of the case;

- education - defines the goals and objectives of education and upbringing integrated into the case-study method;

- science sets the key methodologies, which are defined by analytical activities and the systems approach, as well as many other scientific methods that are integrated into the case and the process of its analysis.

While creating a case, it is necessary to take into account the requirements that it must meet. First of all, the case must have a clear goal, have an appropriate level of difficulty, illustrate several aspects of life (economic, social, political, etc.), must not become outdated too quickly, be relevant for today, illustrate typical situations, develop analytical thinking, provoke a discussion and have several solutions.

Cases vary in complexity, profile, goals, etc. When working with a case, the instructor should teach students the algorithm of case solving, to use various methods, which the student will be able to use later.

Using case studies in our teaching activities, the following technology can be used to work with case studies in the educational process:

- 1) individual work with case materials (identification of a problem, formulation of key alternatives, proposing a solution or a recommended action);

- 2) work in small groups to agree a vision of the key problem and its solutions;

- 3) presentation and examination of the results of small groups in a general discussion (within the study group).

Each case may be solved analytically either individually or in a group. Accordingly, the instructor may indicate the algorithms of case solving and give a reference to the solution methodology when compiling the case.

When composing an author's case, students not only describe a concrete case from their practice, but also offer methodological recommendations on the case solution and give their own solution. At the same time, they master the methodology of making a case, and the situations arising in the tutor's activity are compressed and solved.

We can say that case-study is designed to improve skills and gain experience in the following areas:

- identifying, selecting, and solving problems;
- working with information - comprehending the meaning of details described in the situation;
- analyzing and synthesizing information and arguments;
- working with assumptions and conclusions;
- assessing alternatives;
- decision-making;
- listening and understanding others - group work skills;
- formation of the main competences of a tutor [2].

Thus, new professions require new educational technologies, reformatting of educational space, modern principles of mastering a profession. In particular, with the help of case- study method students and specialists have an opportunity to form necessary professional competences, which help to be competitive and to respond adequately to the challenges of our time.

Cases must meet the following criteria:

1. Accessibility for all participants to understand.
2. Adequacy to the tasks solved by the participants in reality, their daily activities.
3. Adaptability to contemporary reality and the tasks facing contemporary Uzbek education.
4. Wittiness.
5. Friendliness.
6. Morality and tactfulness.
7. Providing space and opportunities for improvisation and creativity of the participants, opportunities to be creative.

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